

Investigating the Contributions of Non-Governmental Organisations Towards Administration of Public Secondary Schools in North-Central, Nigeria

Afolabi, Samson Adeniran, Dr C. I. Tyokyaa. & Dr. G. Ochai

Department of Educational Administration and Planning
Joseph Sarwuan Tarka University Makurdi, Benue state

Abstract

This study investigated the extent of the contributions of Non-Governmental Organizations towards the administration of Public Secondary Schools in North-Central Nigeria. Two research questions were raised in line with two specific objectives to guide the study and seven hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance. The study adopted a survey research design. The population of the study was 65,171, comprising 3179 principals, 61,854 teachers and 138 Non-Governmental Organizations (NGO) officials in North-Central Nigeria. The sample size of the study was 397 which was determined by the application of Taro Yamane's formula. Disproportionate stratified sampling technique was adopted for the study. Self-structured questionnaire titled "Assessment of the Contributions Non-Governmental Organizations on Administration of Public Secondary Schools in North-Central Questionnaire (ACNOTAPS). The instrument was validated by five experts, three of whom were from Department of Educational Administration and Planning and two from Measurement and Evaluation, all from Joseph Tarka University, Makurdi. The reliability of the instrument was established using Cronbach Alpha Coefficient Reliability test and a reliability coefficient of 0.93 was obtained which was considered reliable for the study. Data collected was analyzed using descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation was used to answer the research questions while Chi-square of goodness of fit was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study revealed that Non-Governmental Organization has played a significant role in the funding and enhancing teachers' capacity in Public Secondary Schools in North-Central Nigeria. Based on the findings, it was recommended that, Government and school leadership should foster a formal partnership with Non-Governmental Organization and government education agencies to streamline efforts and avoid duplication of resources.

Keywords; Non-Governmental Organisation, Contribution, Funding, Teachers' Capacity Building, Assessment, Administration.

INTRODUCTION

Education occupies a center stage in Nigeria's social and economic development as it serves as the springboard for social and economic change. Education is both a human right and indispensable means of realizing other human rights. As an empowerment right, education is the primary vehicle by which economically and socially marginalized adults and children can lift themselves out of poverty and obtain the means to participate fully in their communities (Abdullahi, 2022). That means, education helps to develop an individual who turns out to develop the nation. Therefore, education can also be seen as a tool for national development and there is no nation that can grow beyond their level of education. For a nation to develop properly there must be deliberate effort to develop education and for education to be properly developed there is need for proper utilization of the resources available to the education administrator.

Educational Administration is the process of integrating the appropriate human and material resources that are available and make effective use of them to achieve the purposes of programme of an educational institution (Enyi, 2012). In a similar vein, Ajibade (2012) defined educational administration as the process of controlling, organizing, and directing both human and material resources in an educational institution. Okereke (2019) states that school administration involves managing, administering the curriculum, and teaching, pastoral care, discipline, assessment, evaluation and examinations, resource allocation, costing and forward planning, staff appraisal relationship with the community, use of practical skills, necessary for survival of the policies of organization. According to Idoko (2015), educational administration is the systematic arrangement of human and material resources and programmes that are available in education and carefully using them within defined guidelines or policies to achieve educational goals. Educational administration in secondary schools therefore involves the general provision and management of the resources available to the school administrators.

Management and Administration of education in Nigeria is the responsibility of the federal, state, and local government. However, Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs), and (private) individuals participate at all levels in supporting the education sector. The Federal Ministry of Education (FME) plays a leading role in the

management of the sector in the country. To have better administration of education sector in Nigeria, the Federal Government of Nigeria divided the sector into three (3), the primary, secondary, and tertiary education. In this regard, Local Governments are involved in managing primary education under the supervision of State Governments, the state Governments are involved in the establishment and administration of public and government grant aided secondary schools while the Federal Government is more directly involved with tertiary education with some federal unity schools across the nation. Presently, the Nigeria education system is categorized into three sub-sections: 9-3-4 system. That is, Basic Education (9 years), Senior Secondary Education (3 years) and Tertiary Education with minimum of (4 years) (Onyukwu, 2011).

Secondary school covers second part of basic education; that is, Junior Secondary School and Senior Secondary School. Akpakwu (2016) opines that Secondary School aims at preparing students for tertiary education and useful living within the society. State governments are the leading proprietors of Secondary Schools in Nigeria. According to Onyukwu, 2011, the state government is saddled with the responsibility of managing and administering every activity of the secondary schools, beginning from establishment, funding of the school activities, provision and maintenance of educational facilities, teachers' recruitment and development, provision of security for the school and the environment among others. These and many more are the responsibilities of the state government. Moshood (2014) opines that the federal and state government of Nigeria put several policies in place to promote and improve the education sector. Apart from the state government being responsible for the administration of public secondary schools in the states, there are other individual and organizations that had come to support the state government to effectively administer education at this level, these groups of individual and organization are referred to as the Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) (Onyukwu, 2011).

Trump (2015) noted that, in spite of the efforts put in place by the federal, state and local government, there are still several challenges facing education administration in the study area. Adegoke (2019) also states that the education sector of a country like Nigeria cannot be run solely by the government alone; this brings to bear the need for collaborative effort by well to do Nigerians and the Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) locally, nationally, and internationally. The Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) play significant roles in supporting the government in making provision for education in Nigeria and the Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) also serves as important stakeholders who complement the efforts of government in terms of administration of public secondary schools. Administration of secondary schools requires a huge sum of money ranging from the cost of building the school facilities such as classrooms, library, staffroom, school hall, to the provision of educational furniture, provision of learning materials, recruitment, and training of teachers among others. This has huge financial implications on the state government. The dwindling state allocation to education has led to several challenges in educational sector most especially in North-Central of Nigeria (Olutola 2018). When these educational provisions are not met, effective teaching and learning might become difficult and hence falling standard of education.

Consequently, there are several challenges facing public secondary schools in the study area. According to Adegoke (2019), there are several schools that exist without quality building for classrooms while some of the classrooms are dilapidated due to lack of proper maintenance and several classes are without adequate seat for students' use. Teachers who are the main instrument in teaching and learning are sometimes inadequate; those available are being loaded with excess work to cover and without regular training to boost their performance. The state government is also expected to make provision for proper security architecture to ensure safety of the school and the immediate community, to enable the teaching and learning in a secured environment. These needs are becoming a huge task for the state government, and it is negatively affecting the schools and the community at large. To address these challenges several groups and individual comes together as Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) and are putting resources together to support administration of public secondary schools in North-Central Nigeria.

A Non-Governmental Organization (NGO) is an association that works independently of government to fulfill a task or a purpose. The term normally applies to organizations that are neither a part of government, non-profit nor conventional profit-making businesses, the organizations are usually set up by ordinary citizens (Calvin, 2017). However, Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) may get support from governments, foundations, business firms or direct funding by the people. Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) are highly diverse group of individuals and organizations who engaged in a wide range of activities and take different forms in different parts of the world. For instance, some have charitable status, while others may be registered for tax exemption; others may be for political, religious, or other interest groups like human rights, environment, or development work (Moshood, 2014).

In Nigeria there are several Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) who serve as support groups to the provision of education and most importantly in North-Central. Some of the Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) are The Parents' Teachers' Association (PTA), Community Based Organizations, Religious Organizations, Alumni/Alumnus, Community Vigilante group and Philanthropists among others. All these contribute significantly to the administration of Secondary Schools in North-Central of Nigeria. According to Keegan (2011), Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) can be understood by their orientation and level of cooperation and further identified types of non-governmental organization by orientation as, charitable orientation, service orientation, participatory orientation, empowering orientation. Keegan (2011) went further to identify the following types of Non-Governmental Organizations based on cooperation; Community-Based organization, City-Wide organization and International Non-Governmental Organizations among others, and all these Non-Governmental Organizations work together to complement the efforts of the government.

Non-Governmental Organizations are very crucial in supporting education as they work collectively locally, with international organizations, government bodies as well as other Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) to support education. Miller-Grandvaux and Wolf in Mgbodile (2018) stated that most countries in Africa with a donor-supported programme for education play a significant role in managing public secondary schools in the region and further noted that Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) is not limited to education service-delivery only, they are also involved in lobbying and advocating for educational reform, working individually and through networks to participate in policy dialogue in many African countries.

There are several Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) in North-Central Nigeria that work to support education administration. George (2008) noted the presence of several Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) in North-Central of Nigeria that are all working to improve the standard of education. Some of the Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) are there for the purpose of funding schools and for the purpose of teachers' capacity building. These Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) receives support from several donor which would enable them to perform these duties. Amongst other reasons for the presence of Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) in the study area is the provision of educational facilities which includes building of classrooms, teachers' staff room and library among others, for the usage of the school. Some of them are there for the purpose of employing teachers to the schools where teachers are inadequate (Adegoke, 2019). There are some of the Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) that are concerned about the provision of scholarship to secondary school students. Others are there to make provision for security of both the students and the entire community as well. The presence of these Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) had been noticed and some of their contributions to the administration of public secondary schools in North-Central Nigeria had also been noticed but there is a need to assess the extent of their contribution.

Investigating is the process of making judgment about someone or something considering some details or occurrence. According to Shepherd and Godwin (2019), assessment is any systematic methods of obtaining evidence from posing questions to draw inferences about the knowledge, attitudes, and other characteristics of people or their activities over a given period and for a specific purpose. Assessment can be carried out to find out certain activities or the extent of such activities. There are a good number of Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) in North-Central Nigeria that are contributing to the administration of secondary schools with this, there is need to assess the extent of their contributions over time.

In assessing the extent of Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) contributions to the administration of public secondary schools in North-Central Nigeria, the following variables were considered: funding and teachers' capacity building. Funding in education is the process of raising financial resources to cater for educational needs. According to Tyokyaa (2016), fund can be seen as the sum or amount of money made available for a particular purpose. Administration of education requires a lot of money ranging from the cost of the school plant, capital, and recurrent expenses among others. In Nigeria, one of the major problems of education is inadequate funding. According to Ohaegbulem (2023), the Nigeria budgetary allocation to education in the past ten (10) years have been far below the United Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) recommended percentage of 26%; in 2014, 10.6% was allocated to education; in 2015 it was 9.5%; 6.1% was allocated in 2016; 2017 was 7.38%; 2018 was 7.03%; 2019 was 7.2%; 2020 was 6.7%; 2021 was 5.6%; 2022 was 5.4% and 2023 was 5.3%. This inadequate funding has necessitated the presence of several Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) rising to support educational development through funding (Wilson, 2016). The Non-Governmental Organizations support the state government in making provision for funding education so that the objectives of education in North-Central could be met. Apart from the issue of direct funding, the Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) also support administration of public schools in North-Central Nigeria through the development of teachers who are the main agents in teaching activities.

Teachers' capacity building is the process of developing the teachers through training, retraining and workshops. There is a high need for the teachers to be properly and adequately trained in school and need for them to undergo trainings, workshops, and conferences from time to time to enable them to keep updating their knowledge so they can teach effectively. Shaibu and Isah (2018) reiterated that teaching is a unique profession which imparts knowledge to develop a nation. Shaibu and Isah (2018) further added that teachers need to be regularly and adequately trained to update their knowledge and skills to meet the technological changes to carry out their distinctive duties. Odeyemi (2015) is of the view that in all educational establishment, the teaching profession needs more training that will enable teachers to continue to remain relevant in the scheme of things. This is because in a dynamic society with several open sources of acquiring knowledge, the teacher must be properly trained to be able to continue to impart knowledge to the learners both within and outside the classroom environment. It is based on this that several Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) support educations in North-Central Nigeria by organizing training programmes for the teachers. According to Nwokocha (2015), there are several Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) in North-Central Nigeria that support education administration through training and re-training of teachers such as Rhedda Barna Foundation, APASAM Educational Initiative, Parent Teachers Association, Rockefeller Foundations among others. Through training, teachers would be able to perform their jobs effectively. When the teachers are well trained, there is also a need for the educational facilities which will enhance the teaching and to be adequately provided. It is one thing for the teachers to be fully prepared, it is another thing for the adequate environment to be provided. Similarly, Niyi, Evans and Joshua (2023) state that Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) contributes to the teachers' capacity building in Nigeria.

Administration of public secondary schools has to do with the proper coordination of both human and material resources available to achieve the aims and objectives of the school. In school administration, there are several variables that are considered necessary for the smooth running of the schools; some of the variables include the following: funding of the schools, teachers' capacity building, provision of educational facilities, maintenance of educational facilities, provision of scholarship, recruitment of teachers and provision of security among others. These and many more are the requirements needed for effective teaching and learning to take place and for general administration of secondary schools most especially in North-Central Nigeria.

Statement of Problem

The researcher observed that several schools in the study area lack educational facilities. Adegoke (2019) noted that, there are several schools that exist without quality building for classrooms while some of the classrooms are dilapidated due to lack of proper maintenance and several classes are without adequate seat for students' use. It is the duty of the government at the federal and state to make adequate provision of educational facilities in secondary schools, but when the government is unable to make full provision for those needs, the Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) also rise to support them. With the support of the Non-Governmental Organizations, the administration of public secondary schools should become easy for effective teaching and learning.

Although, the federal and state governments are trying their best in making provision for these educational needs in public secondary schools in North-Central Nigeria, however, due to several factors such as finance and insecurities among others, the researcher observed that the challenges are still obvious in the area. It is for these reasons that there are several Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) in North-Central Nigeria making efforts in supporting government to ensure those educational needs are met. Ogbonnaya (2019) states that, despite the efforts by the government at the federal and state levels together with the Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs), the level of education is still very low and the states in North-Central Nigeria are being regarded to as Educationally Less Developed States (ELDS). The public secondary schools in the study area are not properly funded. This could be visibly seen in inadequate facilities and dilapidated educational facilities in the study area. Besides funding is the issue of teachers' capacity building which is highly necessary for effective administration of secondary schools in North-Central of Nigeria. The researcher observed that the schedule training for teachers in the area is not regular enough. Even though there are several Non-Government Organizations (NGOs) in the area with the aim of supporting the teachers' capacity building yet there are several teachers who do not have opportunity to be trained and this makes them ineffective in their job. Inadequate number of teachers in the public secondary schools in North-Central was also observed, where there are some subjects without teachers and some subject teachers are being overloaded with work because of the shortages in the number of teachers. The researcher also observed that several students in the study area are out of school because they cannot afford the cost of public secondary schools and the number of students on scholarship is too low despite the effort of both the government and Non-Government Organizations (NGOs). Besides the issue of dropping out of school because of school fees, there are other students who are out of school because of the level of insecurity in the study area; some teachers are also not willing to work in certain areas because of the high level of insecurity in those areas. How can one achieve effective teaching and learning in an unsecured environment? More worrisome is the fact that there are several government security agencies and even community security agencies in the area, yet the story remains unchanged.

Even though Non-Government Organizations (NGOs) in the area are collaborating with the government in making provision for those educational needs as highlighted above yet, the impact is not visible and there are still several challenges facing administration of public secondary schools in the area. There is, therefore, need to assess the extent of their contributions in this area. It is against this background that this study seeks to assess the extent of the contributions of Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) in funding, teachers' capacity building, provision of educational facilities, maintenance of educational facilities, provision of scholarship, recruitment of teachers and provision of security towards administration of public secondary schools in North-Central Nigeria.

Purpose of the Study

The objective of the study is to assess the extent of contributions of Non-Governmental Organizations (NGO) to the administration of public secondary schools in North-Central Nigeria. Specifically, the study seeks to:

1. examine the extent Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) contribute to funding of public secondary schools.
2. determine the extent Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) contribute to teachers' capacity building in the public secondary schools.

Research Questions

The following research questions are raised to guide the study:

1. What extent do Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) contribute to the funding of public secondary schools in North-Central Nigeria?
2. What extent do Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) contribute to teachers' capacity building in the public secondary schools?

Statement of Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study and will be tested at the 0.05 level of significance.

1. Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) does not significantly contribute to funding of public secondary schools in North-Central Nigeria.
2. Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) does not significantly contribute to teachers' capacity building in public secondary schools in North-Central Nigeria.

METHODOLOGY

Survey Research design was adopted for the study. The population of this study was 65,171 comprising of 3,179 Principals, 61,854 Teachers and 138 Non-Governmental Organization (NGO) officials, in North-Central Geographic Zone, Nigeria. The sample size of the study was 397 which was determined by application of the Taro Yamane formula. Proportional sampling technique was employed the study. Self-structured instrument was subjected to face and content validation by five experts. Three of the experts were from Educational Administration and Planning Department and two were Measurement and Evaluation all from College of Education, Joseph Sarwuan Tarka University, Makurdi. Cronbach's Alpha Reliability Coefficient was used to determine the reliability of the instrument and a reliability coefficient of 0.93 was obtained which was considered reliable for study. Descriptive statistics of Mean and Standard Deviation were used to answer the research questions. Any item with a mean rating ranging from 3.50 to 4.00 was regarded as having a 'Very High Extent' (VHE) contribution, any mean rating from 2.50 to 3.49 was regarded as having a 'High Extent' (HE) contribution, any mean from 1.50 to 2.49 was regarded as having a 'Low Extent' (LE) contribution, and any mean from 1.00 to 1.49 was regarded as having a 'Very Low Extent' (VLE) contribution. To test the hypotheses, the researcher employed the Chi-square (χ^2) goodness-of-fit test at a significance level of 0.05. The decision criterion for the hypotheses was a p-value less than the alpha value (0.05), which was considered statistically significant, indicating a significant contribution. Conversely, a p-value greater than or equal to the alpha value (0.05) was considered not statistically significant, suggesting no significant contribution.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: What extent do Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) contribute to funding of public secondary schools in North-Central Nigeria.

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation of Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) Contributions to Funding of Public Secondary Schools in North-Central Nigeria

S/No	Items	No	Mean	SD	Decision
1	To what extent do Parent Teacher Association, Community Based Organizations and others provide financial contributions to public secondary schools to support schools' expenses in your area?	397	2.41	0.73	Low Extent
2	To what extent do Parent Teacher Association, Community Based Organizations and others organize or fund literary and debate activities of the secondary schools in your area?	397	2.33	0.74	Low Extent
3	To what extent do Parent Teacher Association, Community Based Organizations and others fund the end of the year prize giving activities of the secondary schools in your area?	397	2.54	0.79	High Extent
4	To what extent do Parent Teacher Association, Community Based Organizations and others fund other academic competitions in secondary schools in your area?	397	2.31	0.79	Low Extent
5	To what extent do Parent Teacher Association, Community Based Organizations and others fund sporting activities in secondary schools in your area?	397	2.19	0.78	Low Extent
6	To what extent do Parent Teacher Association, Community Based Organizations and others fund secondary school teachers' welfare scheme that enhances their wellbeing in your area?	397	1.91	0.78	Low Extent
7	To what extent do Parent Teacher Association, Community Based Organizations and others fund excursion programme in secondary schools in your area?	397	2.08	0.78	Low Extent
8	To what extent does NGOs engage in advocacy efforts to influence government funding of public secondary schools in your area?	397	2.30	0.91	Low Extent
Cluster Mean			2.25	0.78	Low Extent

The data presented in Table 1 shows that items 1-8 had mean values of 2.41, 2.33, 2.54, 2.31, 2.19, 1.91, 2.08 and 2.30 with corresponding standard deviation values of 0.73, 0.74, 0.79, 0.79, 0.78, 0.78, 0.78 and 0.91 respectively and a cluster mean of 2.25 and standard deviation 0.78, indicating the low extent. This is based on criteria set for decision making, any items on the table with a mean score of 2.50 and above indicating a high extent and a mean score of below 2.50 is low extent. The outcome of this analysis showed that the contribution of Non-Government Organization through funding of public secondary schools was graded as low extent.

Research Question 2: What extent do Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) contribute to teachers' capacity building in public secondary schools in North-Central Nigeria.

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of the Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) Contribution Towards Teachers' Capacity Building in Public Secondary Schools in North-Central Nigeria

S/ No	Items	No	Mean	SD	Decision
9	To what extent do Parent Teacher Association, Community Based Organizations and others provide training sessions for teachers in public secondary schools in your area?	397	1.98	0.86	Low Extent
10	To what extent do the Parent Teacher Association, Community Based Organizations and others enhance mutual relationship among the teachers, students, parents, and the community in your area?	397	2.45	0.82	Low Extent
11	To what extent do Parent Teacher Association, Community Based Organizations and others offer mentoring duties to teachers of public secondary schools in your area?	397	2.12	0.87	Low Extent
12	To what extent do the educational training provided by the Parent Teacher Association, Community Based Organizations and others for the public secondary schools teachers in your area helps to improve their effectiveness in the school?	397	2.27	0.75	Low Extent
13	To what extent do Parent Teacher Association, Community Based Organizations and others provide training materials for teachers in public secondary schools in your area?	397	2.00	0.85	Low Extent
14	To what extent do Parent Teacher Association, Community Based Organizations and others facilitate the integration of technology in teaching and learning in secondary schools in your area?	397	2.08	0.84	Low Extent
15	To what extent do Parent Teacher Association, Community Based Organizations and others create platforms for teachers to collaborate and learn from one another in your area?	397	2.01	0.68	Low Extent
15	To what extent do the Parent Teacher Association, Community Based Organizations and others provide psychological support training to teachers to enable them support students in trauma in secondary schools in your area?	397	2.03	0.89	Low Extent
Cluster mean			2.11	0.82	Low Extent

The data presented on table 2 indicates that item 9-16 had mean scores of 1.98, 2.45, 2.12, 2.27, 2.00, 2.08, 2.01, and 2.03 with a correspondence standard deviation of 0.86, 0.82, 0.87, 0.75, 0.85, 0.84, 0.68 and 0.89 respectively and a cluster mean of 2.11 and S D 0.82, the result indicating Low extent of Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) contributing to teachers' capacity building in public secondary schools in North-Central Nigeria.

Hypotheses Testing

The hypotheses of the study are tested using chi-square at 0.05 level of significance.

Hypothesis one: Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) do not significantly contribute to funding of public secondary schools in North-Central Nigeria.

Table 3: chi-square test Goodness of fit of Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) do not Significantly Contribute to Funding of Public Secondary Schools in North-Central Nigeria.

Response option	Observed N	Expected N	Df	χ^2	P	Sig level	Remarks
VHE	27	99.3	3	128.69	0.00	0.05	Significant
HE	131	99.3					
LE	173	99.3					
VLE	66	99.3					
Total	397						

P<0.05

Table 3 shows that the chi-squared calculated value of 128.69, df = 3 and a P-value of 0.00 which is less than alpha-value (α) of 0.05 (P<0.05). Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that Non-Governmental

Organizations (NGOs) does not significantly contribute to funding of public secondary schools in North-Central Nigeria is rejected. This implies that Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) contribute significantly to funding of public secondary schools in North-Central Nigeria.

Hypothesis two: Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) do not significantly contribute to teachers' capacity building in public secondary schools in North-Central Nigeria.

Table 4: Chi-square Test Goodness of fit of Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) do not Significantly Contribute to Teachers' Capacity Building in Public Secondary Schools in North-Central Nigeria

Response option	Observed N	Expected N	Df	χ^2	P	Sig level	Remarks
VHE	26	99.3	3	136.67	0.00	0.05	Significant
HE	89	99.3					
LE	189	99.3					
VLE	93	99.3					
Total	397						

P<0.05

Table 4 shows that the chi-squared calculated value of 136.67, df = 3 and a P-value of 0.00 which is less than alpha-value (α) of 0.05 (P<0.05). Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) does not significantly contribute to teachers' capacity building in public secondary schools in North-Central Nigeria is rejected. This implies that Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) significantly contribute to teachers' capacity building in public secondary schools in North-Central Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of the study shows that Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) play a significant role in funding public secondary schools in North-Central Nigeria. The findings of the study align with the previous study of Ibrahim (2023) who maintained that Parent Teachers Association contributes to secondary schools' administration through provision of educational materials such as computers, laboratories, library among others, recruitment, and payment of teachers' salaries to support those who are employed by the government and in the construction of blocks of classroom to enhance teaching and learning. The findings of the study negate the findings of Okunamiri (2015) who asserts that organized communities such as parent teachers association, age grades, did not contribute significantly to funding secondary education. The findings of the study agree with Wilson, (2016) who maintains that inadequate funding has necessitated the presence of several Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) rising to support educational development through funding. The Non-Governmental Organizations support the state government in making provision for funding education so that the objectives of education in North-Central could be met.

Findings of the study also reveal that, Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) have played a significant role in enhancing teachers' capacity in public secondary schools in North-Central Nigeria. The findings of the study support the previous work of Nwokocha (2015), who states that several Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) in North-Central Nigeria support education administration through training and re-training of teachers such as Rhedda Barna Foundation, APASAM Educational Initiative, Parent Teachers Association, Rockefeller Foundations among others. The finding of the study agrees with the previous work of Umar (2016) an overall low level of Non-Governmental Organizations' contributions in the management of public secondary schools in Zamfara State, Nigeria. The study also agrees with the findings of Niyi, Evans and Joshua (2023) which states that Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) contributes to the teachers' capacity building in Nigeria.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the study, it was concluded that the Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) contribute to the administration of public secondary schools in North-Central Nigeria on a low extent and that there is need for improvement. While the contributions may vary in scale, they collectively enhance the educational environment and support the overall goals of improving access to quality education. Collaboration between government educational institutions and Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) can amplify these efforts, ensuring that educational resources are more effectively utilized and accessible to students. The study highlights

the valuable role that Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) play in supplementing government efforts in the educational sector. Moving forward, policymakers and stakeholders should consider fostering stronger partnerships with Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) to leverage their expertise and resources for sustained improvements in public secondary education across the North Central Nigeria.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Government and School leadership should Foster formal partnerships between Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) and government education agencies to streamline efforts and avoid duplication of resources. Clear frameworks and agreements can enhance coordination and maximize the impact of NGO contributions.
2. Government should provide training and capacity-building opportunities for Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) involved in educational support. This can include workshops on effective school management, fundraising strategies, and educational program implementation to ensure NGOs operate more efficiently and sustainably.

References

- Abdullahi, S. U. (2022). *Parent-Teacher Association (PTA) as an instrument of community participation in education*. Musa Publishers.
- Adegoke, O. S. (2019). Appraisal of the adequacy of available school plant for primary education in Ayedaade Local Government Area of Osun State. *Educational Thought*, 4(1), 64-69.
- Ajibade, S. (2012). Supervision: Needed research. *Journal of Curriculum and Supervision*, 5(2), 181-188.
- Calvin, R. M. (2017). *Human relations in organizations*. Times Onitsha: Brooklyn Pub.
- George, T. B. (2008). Introduction. In C. J. De Vita & C. Fleming (Eds.), *Building capacity in nonprofit organizations*. The Urban Institute.
- George, T. B. (2016). The level of secondary school plant provision, utilization, and maintenance in Nigeria. *West African Journal of Education*, 1(2), 165-166.
- Godwin, J. (2019). *Welfare and working conditions: Personnel management* (2nd ed.). Tata McGraw-Hill Publishing Company Limited.
- Ibrahim, E. J. (2017). *Impact of community participation on the development of secondary schools in Niger State, Nigeria* (Unpublished master's dissertation). Ahmadu Bello University, Nigeria.
- Keegan, T. M. (2011). *Using assessment to improve the quality of education*. UNESCO.
- Moshood, T. O. (2014). Role of non-governmental organizations in the development of environmental education: The case of Nigerian Conservation Foundation, Lekki, Lagos State, Nigeria. *Prepared for Commission on Geographic Education Newsletter*. Department of Geography, Bayero University Kano, Nigeria.
- Niyi, J. O., Evans, O. A., & Joshua, O. (2023). Contribution of international organizations to the development of education in Nigeria. *Journal Ilmiah Pendidikan Holistik (JIPH)*, 2(4), 345-356.
- Nwokocha, E. D. (2015). Human resource management in school administration in Delta State, Nigeria. *Journal of Social Sciences*, 23(9), 179-189.
- Oboegbulem, I. A., & Onwurah, I. (2011). *Organization and management of education*. Great AP Express Publisher Ltd.
- Ogbonnaya, M. O. (2000). *Foundation of education finance*. Chuka Educational Publishers.
- Ogbonnaya, M. O. (2019). *Social and political contexts of educational administration*. Chuka Educational Publishers.
- Ohaegbulem, E. U. (2023). Budgetary allocation to education in Africa. *International Journal of Mathematics and Statistics Studies*, 11(4), 32-44. Retrieved from <http://ejournal.org/> on June 17, 2024.

- Okereke, M. I. (2019). *Dynamics of school supervision*. Cheston Books.
- Okuamiri, B. (2015). Ideas to action: Independent research for global prosperity. Center for Global Development Panel on Accountability and Governance in the Voluntary Sector. (1999). *Building on strength: Improving governance and accountability in Canada's voluntary sector*. Retrieved July 21, 2011, from <http://www.vsr-trsb.net/pagvs/>
- Olaniyan, J. H., & Ojo, S. K. (2018). *The principles and practice of teaching*. Joja Educational Research Publishers.
- Olaniyan, O. (2011). The determinants of child schooling in Nigeria. *African Economic Research Consortium, Nairobi, Kenya* (AERC Research Paper 217), 1-49.
- Olutola, A. (2018). Educational facilities and students' performance in West African School Certificate Examination. *International Journal of Educational Management*, 1(1).
- Onyukwu, J. (2011). The education system in Nigeria. Retrieved September 5, 2016, from <http://wenr.wes.org/2011/08/wenr-julyaugust-2011-practical-information/>
- Shaibu, S. J., & Isah, M. G. (2018). Administration of public secondary schools in Nigeria: Problems and suggestions. *European Scholar Journal (ESJ)*, 1(3), 1-11.
- Trump, O. R. (2015). Impact of political influence on the educational sector in Nigeria. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science (IJRISS)*, 2(V), 57-59.
- Tyokyaa, C. I. (2016). *Educational planning and management techniques*. Impart Communications.
- Umar, N. M. (2016). Assessment of contributions of non-governmental organizations in the management of public secondary schools in Zamfara State, Nigeria. *Unpublished master's thesis*, Ahmadu Bello University Zaria, Nigeria.
- Wilson, A. (2016). Social science research: Principles, methods, and practice. Retrieved November 14, 2014, from http://scholarcommons.usf.edu/oa_textbooks/3